

**ORGANIZATION OF INTEGRATED EDUCATIONAL
ACTIVITIES IN DEVELOPMENT CENTERS ON THE BASIS OF
THE "FIRST STEP" STATE CURRICULUM**

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Annotation .

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for children emotional , physical , social and intellectual such as all in the fields development the "Science and Nature" center organizes educational activities " Basics of Science and Natural Sciences/Ecology" .

The main goal of the center is to introduce children to nature and environmental phenomena, to distinguish living and non-living nature, to learn about the ways of living of various creatures in it, and to learn about ecology.

In the center of "Science and Nature". **The experiments carried out** in the center " Basics of science and natural sciences/ecology" in connection with educational activities arouse interest in children and encourage them to make new inventions.

Children think during the study of natural materials, discover games, inventions and small scientific experiments designed to gain knowledge for themselves, in which concepts of natural science are formed.

Preschool children are enriched with the concepts of environmental protection and keeping the world around us clean. Special performances on the theme of preservation of mother nature are organized based on scenarios.

Equipment for conducting experiments in the "Science and Nature" center: sand, water, plants, seeds, containers of various shapes and colors, various fruits, wheat ears, flour, pictures of bakery products, cotton buds, pictures, seeds, cotton products, environmental games, lotto games, magnifying glass, compass, binoculars, microscope, battery, magnet, nature corner, children's tools, soil in a special container, water, shovels, small bulbs, necessary materials for the game "Soap bubbles" are prepared.

At the center, by gaining knowledge about where the things we use in our lives come from, what they are made from, our relationship with them changes in a positive way. For example, it is very interesting for children to see that bread comes to our table, that oil comes out of a cotton seed by crushing it, that there is no oil in a watermelon seed, that an onion grows when it is placed in a glass of water with its root, and that the seeds sprout when they are sprinkled in pots.

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In this center, they get basic knowledge about the human body, safety rules for using microscopes, electric tools, kitchen equipment, and getting to know the properties of stone, water, and soil. So, we once again admitted that the main task of the center is aimed at developing cognitive processes in children.

Center activity more adults with together organize will be done . Because children safety provide it is necessary To the center to be placed equipment all for the child's life risk from comparison far away to be provide it is necessary them from used after from the center take is placed . These are the experiences photos taken _ with children received knowledge is strengthened .

When there is a need to use equipment on the theme of the week, experiments conducted with the help of a teacher are organized with other children in the morning and evening hours. When establishing the center, attention should be paid to the following:

1. Any item or product brought to the center is subject to inspection. Focus on where it was developed.
2. The center should be free of objects and equipment with sharp edges and dangerous to the child's life.
3. The center should have various equipment and materials based on nature, photographs of the surrounding environment, educational games, and themes.

Science and Nature Center

"Birds are our friends"

The goal:

Intellectual skills

Expanding children's imagination about flying birds, their living conditions, feeding, reproduction, adaptation to flight.

Continue to train labor skills such as taking care of birds in a cage, changing the water of a bird in a cage, giving grains and greens.

Research-knowledge and efficient reflexive activity

Caring for birds in a cage, changing the water of a bird in a cage, giving grains and greens.

Artistic and creative abilities

How to make origami birds from paper

Necessary equipment and materials: Pictures of flying birds , ICT slides, pictures related to the topic, educational game cards.

Your activity to go :

1. Conversation based on pictures on the topic "Birds are our friends".
2. Slide show.
3. Questions and answers about the topic .
4. for caged birds
5. How to make origami birds from paper
6. Discussion and conclusions.

Additional: an educational game appropriate to the topic, memorizing a poem about birds, drawing a picture of a bird and giving it to friends as a gift.

Noteworthy **aspect:** children's expression of their feelings, attention and mood.

Origami birds

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